

Abeng for multispecies' flourishing

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In this project/poster we present a collaborative poetic inquiry (Sameshima et al., 2017) that draws upon our overlapping sets of expertise as mathematics, science and quantitative literacy educators. We use as our prompt the metaphor of “breath in our bones” and start with the literal – how the atmosphere comes to life in our multispecies kin (Tsing et al., 2019). Shifting scales and working to bring light to the shadows that continue to be cast by plantation practices associated with the founding of the modern world economy—slavery, racism, genocide, and ecocide we attempt to signal that without multispecies' flourishing (Khan, 2020; Tran et al., 2020) the probability of widespread human flourishing is limited. We draw upon an analogy with the abeng as we present examples from our practice as teacher educators.

C de breath in dese bones

*Who listens to the earth, to the species on it?
Who feels the shortness of their breath?
Whose job is it to give warning?
Most cultures have had elders or spiritualists to give the call,
to listen to the world,
to read and write the world and the word,
to blow the abeng,
to cause us to gather.
If not mathematicians, scientists, technologists and educators then who?*

*I think it needs to be more explicit.
It is the colonial cultures,
the ‘more developed world’,
the old and new Empires
that have contributed most of the carbon.
They have stolen the pathways
from “‘lesser’ developed” to “‘more’ developed.”
Unjust as colonialist countries stole people, culture, resources,
they’ve stolen an ‘easy’ future,
they’ve stolen the breath in our bone*

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*by handcuffing those country's options for advancement.
All we have left are uneasy futures.*

*There is power in the Abeng
Gaia's call
The earth a breathing being, exhaling
inhaling...
Climate change as Earth's call...
the Abeng as humanity's call...?
Last call.*

In what way might poetry inform the epistemic foundations of mathematics/science/technology?

Drawing upon the framing of ethnomathematics as mythopoetic curriculum (Khan, 2011) – a third approach in Curriculum Studies that establishes the imagination as central to curriculum work and brings together progressive and critical approaches in post-Industrialized contexts – we consciously and humbly draw upon an analogy with the *abeng*, a Ghanian word meaning an animal's 'horn.' The *abeng* is the archae¹-texture anchoring our work. The blowing of the horn in the West Indies called slaves to the sugarcane plantations and allowed Maroon² armies to communicate among themselves (Cliff, 1984/1995). Today, 'New World' Africans blow the *abeng* symbolically as "a call to arm themselves...to stand up and defend their culture and traditions against extinction" (Abengcentral, n.d.).

As we ponder the breath in our bones, we wonder, what are changes in the composition of that atmosphere—the breath in our bones— due to rising anthropogenic carbon dioxide and human activity (e.g., logging/mining) doing to the bodies/bones of our multispecies kin? Our inquiry draws on recent scientific research into nutrient de-densification (Ebi & Loladze, 2019; Loladze et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2018) ocean acidification (Mekkes et al., 2021), changing seasonal patterns (Karrow, Khan & Fleener, 2018), biophonic 'desertification' (Krause, 2012), which we use as examples in our practice as teacher educators. Our poetic representations will be multimodal/synaesthetic, including poetic verse, visual data stories (graphs and infographics), photographs and soundscape. Some examples are included. Our work is a form of *sympoetics*, riffing off of Helmreich's (2009) *sympolitics*. In this sense, "A breath of our mouth becomes the portrait of the world" (Herder, quoted in Heidegger, 1971/1975, p. 139) and a poetic call to gather our marooned communities together. Our choice to use poetry is very much influenced by Feyerabend (2001).

Hearing the rhythm, pulse and pattern of data requires an attuning to its details – its silences and its rhythm - just as one listens to music. To many it would appear that the data

¹ Archaea are unicellular prokaryotes, obligate anaerobes, evolutionarily distinct from bacteria and other eukaryotes. The first species identified were known as extremophiles. They are important in oceans and in the microbiome of all species.

² Maroons were communities formed by slaves and Indigenous peoples who escaped plantations. These communities continue to exist today in the Caribbean.

representing climate change is akin to listening to Lou Reed’s “Metal Machine Music” at full volume; incoherent, grating and without meaning or merit (to the casual listener the album sounds like a microphone buried in badly functioning industrial equipment occasionally being beaten with a sledgehammer). When one reads comments in news media posts about climate change one sees the raging voices of those to who the music of climate data seems to be just that (Bowen & Rodger, 2008). To a climate scientist that data is a rising orchestra of sound, an opera with more and more instruments and more and more singers joining in heading collectively towards a terrible climax, a crescendo followed by a sharp fall with a single keening, voice at the end slowly and plaintively fading away. Climate scientists don’t want that opera, don’t want that crescendo, don’t want that outcome, do not want an opera in which everyone dies.

Quantitative literacies are important in rendering sensible (sense-able) the connections among multiple movements towards justice for example racial justice, ecological justice and economic justice. When combined with other multiliterate and multimodal practices, a focus on multispecies’ flourishing and interdisciplinary practice decenters (but does not devalue) D’Ambrosio’s (2010) ideas of mathematics as a means for human survival with dignity and as a means to more peaceful coexistence and extends it to our many multispecies partners on this planet and their impact on our mathematical attentions.

Figures

(left) A healthy ocean snail has a transparent shell with smoothly contoured ridges. (right) A shell exposed to more acidic, corrosive waters is cloudy, ragged, and pockmarked with ‘kinks’ and weak spots. Photos courtesy Nina Bednarsek, NOAA PMEL.

Figure 1: Scientific photograph of changes affecting shell integrity due to ocean acidification. (Image credit: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration)

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Figure 2: Representations of missing nutrients in plants under elevated CO₂ levels. Left image S. Khan, Right image Irakli Lolozde (2014)

Figure 3: Spring melt and tapping the sugar maples. (Images D. Karrow)

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